

The right way to defeat coronavirus!

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Abstract:

The high tide of coronavirus (COVID-19) has hit us again and again! And there are likely to be more deadly repeated hits in the future. There is no way to stop this deadly virus. In this time of deep crisis, I have come up with two great ways to prevent viral infections including proper treatment of viral infections that can save countless lives. These methods will be effective in multiple ways. They are able to inactivate the virus and block and prevent the virus from entering the body cells. And the vaccine and the medicine I made will heal the person infected by the virus. And they are not harmful to the body.

Coronavirus (Covid-19) is a deadly infectious disease that has killed many people around the world and caused terrible illness. Not only that, the virus has destroyed the entire economic structure, including trade and commerce. Enough effective treatments for this pandemic have not yet been discovered. In this situation, a great way to defeat this virus has been invented by special nanomedicine. This nanomedicine can be considered as a highly effective way to combat coronavirus. It is noteworthy here that this treatment method does not have any side effects like conventional vaccines.

Keywords:

Coronavirus, Disease X, Deadly viruses, Pandemic, Vaccine, COVID-19, Nanotechnology, Nanomedicine,

Introduction:

In the current deep crisis, there is no need to introduce the deadly evil coronavirus that is being discussed everywhere. Nevertheless, I have to say a few words about this virus in this context. Coronavirus (COVID-19) originated in Wuhan, China, according to various scientists. Then it gradually infected millions of people worldwide. The rapid spread of COVID-19 has killed scores of people worldwide and still continues to cause infectious

deaths. Typically, COVID-19 infections are caused by physical contact, airborne cough, and respiratory mucus particles. The main symptoms of the infection are fever, cough, weakness, shortness of breath, headache, sore throat, nausea, diarrhea, abdominal pain, etc. Eventually, the virus infected the lungs and killed people with severe respiratory distress, causing great concern. Now I want to introduce you to a powerful way to defeat this evil virus. Vaccines have been and are being developed in different ways in different laboratories. Here I will shed light on an excellent vaccine that I have found to be the best method in my long research, as well as a very effective medicine.

Highly effective ways have been found to defeat the Coronavirus!

Extremely subtle medicine is needed to seize the invisible enemy such as Coronavirus. My Vaccine and medicine will not only heal the infected person, but also act as a preventive. That is why with the help of proper nanoparticle medicine or nanomedicine we can get the best results.

Now, let me first talk about the vaccine I invented:

There are some disadvantages to conventional vaccines. So in order to get the full benefits of the vaccine and at the same time to make the evil free vaccine, we have to prepare the best vaccine in the following way invented by me.

The best way to make the most effective and harmless vaccine is, you have to make a special type of nanoparticles medicine from the infected or diseased cells of a patient infected with the virus or from the saliva of that patient's mouth.

This nano-medicine vaccine has to be prepared through repeated mixing and friction methods. This will create the opposite existence of diseased cells. Which will combine with the diseased cells to destroy both. When this specially formulated nanomedicine reaches the body and combines with the diseased cells, both will be destroyed. I have discussed this in detail in my article 'S-existence and its contrary existence'. And I named this medical procedure 'MahaPathy' briefly 'MPathy'.

If this nanomedicine is prepared properly, everyone will be amazed at its healing power.

The process of making this nanomedicine in a special way is as follows:

To make this nanomedicine, first one part of the original substance or sick cells have to be taken. Then mix nine parts of other (almost) inert material with it and rub it continuously through mortar and pestle for three hours. After rubbing for three hours, one part of the rubbed material should be mixed with nine parts of the (almost) inactive or inert material as before and the rubbing process should be continued for three hours continuously. This friction process is best done with the help of a machine. In this form, after rubbing a total of six times, nanomedicine will be ready.

Not only will this nanomedicine destroy toxins and diseased cells, it will also stimulate partially diseased cells to heal and fight disease. Will activate the immune system against the disease. If this nanomedicine is made with important substances in the structure of the body, then it will help to heal the body by eliminating the deficiency of that essential substance and by removing the contamination or distortion of that substance.

I have discussed in detail how this particular nanomedicine works in the body in the S-existence article.

This time I will talk about my invented another nanomedicine:
Nanoparticles of these ingredients are needed to make this medicine.

Formula of oral medication:

- 1) Phosphate of Iron (Ferric phosphate) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 2) Chloride of potash (Potassium chloride) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 3) Phosphate of potash (Potassium phosphate) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 4) Sulfate of Potash (Potassium Sulphate) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 5) Calcium sulphate (Gypsum) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 6) Calcium carbonate (Carbonate of Lime) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 7) Animal Carbon (Animal Charcoal) (in Nanoparticle form)
- 8) Iodide of Potassium (in Nanoparticle form)

9) Iodide of Sodium (Sodium iodatum) (in Nanoparticle form)

10) Sodium Sulphate (Sulphate of Soda) (in Nanoparticle form)

The medicines given in this formula can be divided into two parts (S-1 & S-2) and taken alternately as two different medicines to get better results.

If we take a look, we can understand that all the substances that have been taken here as medicine ingredients are our body-ingredients. These are very effective in solving various problems of the body in the form of nanoparticles. Each of the ingredients mentioned here has been applied to patients many times and their effectiveness has been successfully demonstrated.

These ingredients need to be mixed in equal parts. Taking 100 mcg (μg) from this mixture, a dose will be prepared by mixing it with twenty drops of water or alcohol or half a gram of something else neutral substance.

If this medicine is applied in the right dosage, it will not have any side or adverse effects. If the patient has any symptoms other than the symptoms of coronavirus infection, or any other disease, then other medicines can be applied along with this medicine as required.

Rules for taking medicine:

Take one dose once or twice a day as a preventive. If someone is diagnosed as corona positive, take one dose four to six times daily.

Mode of action:

This method is used to protect against the virus in two ways.

Its one part acts as an in vitro antiviral against various strains of the virus. It inactivates the virus and blocks or prevents the virus from entering the body cells. Another part of this method is able to heal the cells infected by the virus. And it is not harmful to the body.

Pharmacokinetics:

The nanoparticles of this medicine are all part of our body, so the body can easily accept it. In the nanoparticle state, the components of this medicine have special efficacy and

healing powers. These medicines activate the body's cells and immune system against the enemy and help in the reconstruction of damaged cells. Then it becomes extinct by itself.

The unique efficacy of each component of the medicine in nanoparticle form (very briefly):

1) Phosphate of Iron (in Nanoparticle form): It is extremely effective in lung problems. Quickly relieves acute damage to bronchitis and tuberculosis. Inflammatory, fibrillar, irritating, corrosive, able to cure and repair damage in the first stage of all inflammation, irritations and fever. Especially in the case of catarrhal inflammation of the respiratory tract.

2) Chloride of potash (in Nanoparticle form): It is highly prevalent in subcutaneous or second stage inflammation, fibrinous exudation, and catarrhal tenderness in cases of glandular swelling. It activates the cells and boosts the immune system.

3) Phosphate of potash (in Nanoparticle form): It is very effective in various neurological problems. It is very effective in various problems of the nervous system like nervous weakness and fatigue, tension etc. It boosts nerves and boosts mental strength and kills germs and prevents putrefaction.

4) Sulfate of Potash (in Nanoparticle form): It is very effective in the third stage of any inflammation. Able to disinfect and inactivate viruses. It refreshes and activates the cells and helps in repairing the damage done to the cells.

5) Calcium sulphate (in Nanoparticle form): It is able to cure gland swelling, cystic tumors, fibroids, pus origin, cell damage. It replenishes cell damage and enhances immunity.

6) Calcium carbonate (in Nanoparticle form): It is effective in case of swelling of throat and submaxillary glands. Hawking-up of mucus. Difficult swallowing. Goitre. Parotid fistula. |Cough thick, yellow, bloody mucus with chest pain. Severe chest pain from the back. Chest is very sensitive to touch or pressure. Longing for fresh air.

7) Animal Carbon (in Nanoparticle form):

It plays a very active role in curing various problems of throat, gland and lung infections. Great for weak people and the elderly who have very little vitality.

8) Iodide of Potassium (in Nanoparticle form): It works exclusively on fibers and connective tissues. Prevents anything from outside from entering the cell. Eliminates glandular swelling. Cures infectious fever. Closes the formation of mucous membrane lesions and nodes. Potassium iodide destroys syphilis and tuberculosis bacteria. Effective in respiratory or bacterial respiratory problems. Chronic illness often brings favorable reactions.

9) Iodide of Sodium or Sodium iodatum (in Nanoparticle form): stimulates cellular activity and increases oxidation and metabolism. It is used largely in cardiac cases, pneumonia, asthma, chronic bronchitis, scrofula, tertiary syphilis.

10) Sodium Sulphate (in Nanoparticle form): It helps in expelling toxins from the body through unnecessary aqueous parts of the body.

In addition to this a new life-giving formula to save the life of a patient in a dangerous or fatal condition.

In the critical condition of the patient, the S-3 medicine along with the aforesaid medicines (S-1 & S-2) should be mixed with distilled water and injected like saline. However, this formula is not only effective for patients with coronavirus, but also for patients with low oxygen levels, shortness of breath and dehydration.

Formula of S-3 :

1. Sodium Chloride (in Nanoparticle form)
2. Oxygen / Ozone (in Nanoparticle form)
3. Phosphate of Magnesia (in Nanoparticle form)
4. Calcium Phosphate (in Nanoparticle form)

10 mcg of each medicine should be mixed with 10 ml of distilled water. Once the dangerous condition has passed, the dose of the medicine should be reduced.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this medicine will cure not only coronavirus infections, but also various difficult and complex diseases and even black fungus at an early or acute stage.

References:

The scientific thoughts...

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MahaPathy: A new invented system of medical treatment.

<https://www.kobo.com/us/en/ebook/mahapathy>

Author Bio.:

Maharshi MahaManas (Sumeru Ray)

The word MahaManas means Great Mind or Cosmic Mind!

MahaManas is a great-minded wise sage of the modern age, master of reasonable spirituality, a multi-talented creator, researcher, writer, philosopher, awakener, educator, multifaceted free thinker and he is self-dedicated to human development.

Maharshi MahaManas being sympathetic to the suffering of the helpless troubled human he has worked tirelessly all his life to alleviate their misery and poverty.

He understood from his deep thinking and experience that the root cause of most of the problems and mishaps caused by human beings is lack of adequate knowledge and consciousness and illness of body and mind. Most problems will be solved if the human mind develops enough. That is why he has created an excellent and incomparable mind-development education system, its name is 'MahaManan' education.

Also he is the creator of a new religion based on human development called 'MahaDharma' (Mahaism).

If we can implement his multifaceted revolutionary work and thought, then there will surely be a radical change in human life. All that is needed for this is a strong team dedicated to the cause of real human development in the path shown by him.

He did not look at all our problems from above or from the surface. He has found the root cause of the problem and discovered the way to its real solution.

He is truly a free-spirited science-minded man. He did not try to find solution by flying in the sky with the wings of imagination. His every thought has moved forward along the path of reasoning~ judgment and reality.

It would not be an exaggeration to call him the great sage of the modern times who sees the truth. He has made many scientific discoveries in his search for the truth of life and cosmic life.

It was not at all happy for him to continue his search for truth. He did not think of his own happiness and prosperity, but he had to endure a lot of hardships and obstacles for the welfare of human beings and went ahead tirelessly in search of the way of real liberation of the human beings. This is how the great doctrine of this time~ 'MahaVad' (Mahaism) was born.

He is the pioneer of reasonable spirituality and the creator of the great doctrine~ 'MahaVad', and the founder of 'MahaDharma' –the religion of free-thinkers for true self-development & human development.

Maharshi is well experienced physician of Alternative Medicines, he is a very successful practitioner and researcher in the field of Alternative Medicines and Human Development. MahaManas is the inventor of the new system of medicine~ MPathy...

He is a knowledge worshipper, educated in the open school of the world! Self-conscious and self-aware man of vast experience with art sense, creative power, computer and technological knowledge, new inventory ideas.

He is a good mentor. He is an author – philosopher –researcher. Maharshi MahaManas is the founder teacher of true self/ mind development Education 'MahaManan' and specialist in mental problems. Most important identity of MahaManas, –he is a humanitarian. His all efforts are– for human welfare. He is a social reformer.

He has knowledge in fine arts, literature, Yoga, meditation, art of healing, self-development program, lyric, story, screenplay writing, music composing and film making, news paper and periodicals editing, and reasonable spirituality.

To know more, go through Google search= Sumeru Ray / Maharshi MahaManas

Thank you.

With best regards,

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